

MAPK Signaling Pathway: A Key Player in Rheumatoid Arthritis Pathogenesis

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Conflict of interest: None

ABSTRACT

Chronic inflammation in RA is caused by abnormal regulation of a communication network within cells. This network consists of extracellular stimuli including chemokines, cytokines, and matrix-degrading enzymes which influence the cells to participate in inflammatory processes. These mediators released in the extracellular matrix bind to receptors on the plasma membrane and activate or inactivate intracellular transcription pathways. This paper demonstrated the role of the MAPK cascade in inflammatory signal transduction pathways. It is significant for the maintenance, regulation, and induction of chronic inflammation in RA, and therefore its components can act as potential molecular targets for MAPK inhibitors to control and inhibit inflammation. There is evidence of specific activation of the p38 MAPK pathway in inflammatory arthritis and joint diseases. Here we describe the regulation, function, and activation of MAPK specifically p38 MAPK as well as the role of this pathway in the disease.

Keywords: MAPK , Joints disease Management, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Pathophysiology, cell signaling

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis is a multifaceted autoimmune disorder characterized by pain and swelling of joints synovial inflammation, and cartilage destruction. It doesn't only cause joint irregularities but various other symptoms including anemia, fever, muscle weaknesses, and osteoporosis that can dysregulate functions of the nervous, urinary, and cardiovascular systems. Generally, it is believed that genetic and environmental factors are involved in causing RA because the exact cause remains unknown. There is an involvement of joints being mistakenly attacked by the immune system causing joint capsule thickening of synovial fluid and inflammation and causing damage to cartilage and bones at specific sites. (1). During later stages of the disease, intense degrees of deformity and rigidity of joints are observed, causing skeletal muscle atrophy, bone corrosion, and damage of tendons and ligaments. RA impacts other extra-articular organs and tissues including nerves, kidneys, eyes, skin, lungs, bones, heart, and liver. (2) The development and promotion of rheumatoid arthritis are caused by abnormal signaling pathways of various cytokines. Joints which are local inflammatory sites in RA, abnormality in signaling transduction pathways can lead to the release of pro-inflammatory mediators in excessive amounts which leads to the proliferation of fibroblast-like synoviocytes (FLS) (3). Different signaling pathways

involved in RA pathology include MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinase pathway), Nf-Kb, P13K pathway, and JAK/STAT signaling cascade.

MAPK SIGNALING PATHWAY IN RA

MAPK pathway includes different cascade proteins including extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) A-RAF, BRAF, C-RAF, and mitogen-activated protein MEK. Many extracellular stimuli can activate MAPK pathways including hormones, neurotransmitters, stress conditions, inflammatory and growth factors, and certain viruses (4). MAPK differs involved in regulating different processes in the cell including cell differentiation, cellular proliferation, and apoptosis. MAPK signaling is divided into major three subfamilies comprising P38, ERK, and JNK (c-Jun N terminal Kinase). MAPK pathway activation is done through a three-layer kinase module. MAP3k is activated by phosphorylation which in turn activates MAP2K and then MAPK is activated. Abnormal activation or excessive signaling of MAPK can cause RA (5).

SIGNALING CASCADES IN THE MAPK PATHWAY

ACTIVATION OF ERK1/2, JNK, AND P38 IN THE MAPK PATHWAY

ERK1/2 controls the different activities like cell differentiation, proliferation, and survival of the cell. This pathway can be activated by stimuli such as neurotransmitters, oxidative stress, and

ischemia (6). The first enzyme in the ERK signaling is RAF and has three different isoforms. The main component of the ERK signaling pathway is MEK. In the presence of a stimulus, activated RAS protein binds to RAF protein's N terminus and causes its activation. RAF in response activates MEK through phosphorylation. MEK then phosphorylates and causes activation of ERK1 and ERK2. B-RAF is an isoform of RAF that has the highest efficacy in phosphorylating and activating ERK1/2 (7)

The JNK signaling cascade is initiated through phosphorylation after binding certain factors like inflammatory cytokines, environmental stimuli, GPCR growth factors, and agonists to cell surface receptors. These ligands phosphorylate the Rho family GTPase enzymes in the plasma membrane and activate the proximal membrane protein component such as MKK4/7. JNK is then specifically activated by these activated MAP3Ks by dual phosphorylation at the tyrosine and threonine sites of JNK. MKK4/7 are activated by separate MAP3Ks and have distinguished biochemical properties. Mainly cytokines activate MKK7 which then phosphorylates JNK and activates it. On the other hand, environmental stress activates MKK4 which then activates JNK and p38 (8).

P38 MAPK pathway can respond to many extracellular stimuli like ultraviolet radiations, growth factors, oxidative stress, and cytokines which cause its activation. Various MAP3Ks cause the activation of MAP2Ks, particularly MKK3 and MKK6 which are upstream enzymes in the MAPK pathway and are involved in the regulation of p38 (9).

MAPK SIGNALING' ROLE IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

Rheumatoid arthritis' synovium is comprised of numerous inflammatory cells i.e. macrophages and mast cells. In the injured tissue of joints, MAPK is involved in downstream signal cascade regulation of TNF α receptors and interleukins IL-1 and IL-17. It is also involved in pro-inflammatory cytokines production. ERK1/2 plays an important role production of TNF α in LPS (lipopolysaccharide stimulating macrophages) and interleukins involving IL-6,12 and 23 (10). It also controls Cyclooxygenase-2 dependent prostaglandin E2 production influenced by the release of EGF, released by fibroblast-like synoviocytes (FLS) in rheumatoid arthritis patients (11).

P38 MEDIATED INFLAMMATORY RESPONSES IN RA

P38 is considered the most significant member of the MAPK cascade because of its inflammatory responses in RA. After the stimulation of inflammatory factors, p38 is induced and activated in immune cells including monocytes and neutrophils. P38 is then localized into the nucleus and it stimulates the activation of many transcription factors (TFs) and protein kinase enzymes by phosphorylation that are involved in the regulation of cellular and humoral autoimmune responses. In RA, there is an activation and overexpression of p38 by MKK3/6 in synovial fluid (12). This overexpressed p38 localizes to the nucleus and activates various TFs like MEF2C AND ATF2. These factors initiate signaling pathways that induce a huge increase in the expression of inflammatory cytokines for example monocyte chemoattractant protein (MCP-1) and IL-8 causing the thickening of synovial fluid.

P38 can also influence and stop the process of cell apoptosis. Phosphorylation of p38 induced by integrin activation inhibits cell apoptosis mediated by death receptor FAS, which causes abnormal infiltration of T cells in synovial fluid in huge amounts resulting in the progression of the disease. This imbalance of helper T1/T2 cells causes abnormal secretion of cytokines including IL-2 and IL-4. Another abnormally secreted cytokine IL-17 causes downregulation of the NF-KB signaling pathway, p65 and AP-1. MAPK and p38 mediated abnormal T cell infiltration in synovial fluid plays an imperative role in the progression of rheumatoid arthritis and therefore p38 is considered a possible target for the treatment of the disease (13). The most important role of JNK of MAPK signaling cascade in RA is cartilage destruction mediated by matrix metalloproteinase enzymes (MMPs). Tumor necrosis factor $TNF\alpha$ and $IL-1\beta$ promote and enhance the degradation of extracellular matrix by controlling the expression of matrix metalloproteinases in FLS and articular chondrocytes by activating downstream JNK pathway (14) (15).

MAPK INHIBITORS FOR THE TREATMENT OF RA

P38 kinase is targeted for therapy in patients of RA in preclinical trials but promising inhibitors are yet to be found. Studies have proved that a MAPK P38 inhibitor VX-702 when coupled with inflammatory biomarker inhibitors has the most effective clinical efficacy against RA but may not have a sustainable and meaningful inhibitory response to chronic inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis. An active oral inhibitor of p38, SCIO-469 has not shown any greater positive response

than placebo in RA patients (16). Chondrocytes are protected from hypertrophy by another p38 inhibitor named Pamapimod by inhibition of MEF2C signaling in arthritis. Because p38 MAPK has pleiotropic effects on the immune system, MAPK inhibitory drugs have been successful in preclinical inflammatory studies but have not shown promising effects during clinical trials (Ferguson and Gray.,2018). Moreover, collagen-induced arthritis symptoms have shown reduction by the use of AS601245 which is a JNK inhibitor (17).

DISCUSSION

The release of some pro-inflammatory cytokines causes the induction and activation of signaling pathways related to RA, which in turn results in mesenchymal cell activation and the recruitment of adaptive and innate immune processes coupled with synoviocyte activation. It also causes the activation of different mediators such as IL-1, IL-6, and TGF- α , causing increased angiogenesis, decreased lymphangiogenesis, and increased inflammation of synovial tissue. MAPK is an important signaling cascade for the regulation of different cell processes like migration, cellular survival, cell cycle progression, cellular metabolism, differentiation, and apoptosis as well as gene expression. Its overactivation results in the articular destruction of cartilage and synovial tissue's inflammatory hyperplasia. P38 MAPK activation in synovial tissue causes paracrine, endocrine, and even autocrine activation through proinflammatory cytokines. P38 MAPK activation is also critical for various roles of endothelial cells like vasodilation, angiogenesis, and chemoattraction (18). Chemoattraction is an important event in synovial tissue inflammation because most of the cells in synovium have translocated from blood and crossed the barrier of endothelial cells. MAPK acts as a key sensor of extracellular or intracellular stress. Strong activation of p38 MAPK is experienced in the synovial membranes of patients having rheumatoid arthritis. Synovial vessel's endothelium is the prime location for the expression of active p38 MAPK (19). The insights into signaling pathways involved in RA can serve to elaborate important targets for the treatment of arthritis. Effective inhibitors designed to specifically and effectively inhibit different protein kinases can help in controlling the disease and broadening the spectrum to treat rheumatoid arthritis.

CONCLUSION

Numerous signaling cascades involved in RA are linked to many different signaling molecules other than cytokines. It is important to understand their mechanism of action to fully gain insights into their regulatory, chemoattractive, mitogenic, and proinflammatory characteristics that result in chronic inflammation in RA. MAPK P38 is the main signaling pathway whose abnormal functioning would add to the progression of inflammatory joint disease. Present data reveals that stress kinases affect the regulation, expression, and pathophysiological function of p38 that influence various processes in inflamed joint synovial tissue. These insights are significant to judge during the selection of treatments and drugs to inhibit tissue destruction and inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis.

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